

Biodiversity and conservation of smut fungi (Ustilaginomycetes p.p. and Microbotryales) reflected in Vánky, Ustilaginales exsiccata no. 1-1250

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Received: June 9, 2004 / Accepted: June 15, 2004

Abstract. The alarming loss of biodiversity of the earth is briefly mentioned, to show the importance of herbaria in the inventory and conservation of gene-pools of plants and fungi in general, and those of smut fungi by the activity of H.U.V. (Herb. Ustil. Vánky) in special.

Key words: check-list, exsiccata, smut fungi

Introduction

Alarming reports about the destruction of natural habitats all over the world are frequently published in newspapers, in scientific publications or are shown on TV. For example, “Every minute, the area of the forests of the globe is diminishing by 26 Hectare (= 37 football fields)”. Or, “Every hour 3 species of animals and plants become extinct, which makes each day 70, each month 2100, each year 25 000 extinct species!”. Destruction of natural habitats is usually man-made, as a direct or indirect consequence of the population explosion. But once gone species are extinct for ever. The global biodiversity is yearly becoming less diverse by losing all these species, many of them before they were discovered and described.

Keeping the population explosion under control, as well as increasing our efforts to preserve the natural habitats of the earth, with all possible measures, should be the major problem on all society levels of each country of the world. Inventory of all habitats and all groups of biota of the earth would only be a small part of these measures. In the conservation of the gene-pools of plants and fungi, herbaria play an important role.

The Herbarium Ustilaginales Vánky (H.U.V.) is a private herbarium. It started its activity in 1954 in Romania, continued in Sweden (between 1970-1986) and in Germany (1986-). The

H.U.V. manages a collection of smut fungi (Ustilaginomycetes p.p. and Microbotryales, Basidiomycota), containing at present 20 770 samples, of which a great number are type specimens (holotypes, isotypes, neotypes, lectotypes, syntypes, paratypes, topotypes). The H.U.V. arranges exchange of smut fungi on a one-to-one basis. The H.U.V. also issues and distributes an exsiccata of smut fungi, ‘Vánky: Ustilaginales exsiccata’ (Vánky, Ust. exs.), including smut fungi from all over the world. It is the sole exsiccata of smut fungi appearing after World War II. On 15 June 2004, fascicles XLIX-L (No. 1201-1250) of the exsiccata appeared. Nos. 1-800 were distributed each in 70 samples, nos. 801-1000 in 45 samples, and nos. 1001-1250 in 33 samples (= 73 250 samples). Nearly 70 000 smut fungus specimens of the exsiccata were distributed to mycological herbaria or sent to mycologists from all over the world. The **1250 numbers** of the exsiccata represent **65 smut fungus genera** (of the total known 78 genera), **554 smut fungus species** (of the total *ca* 1450 species), on **754 host plant taxa**. In the exsiccata **134 type specimens** have been distributed.

On the occasion of issuing the 50th fascicle, a revised **General Index** was prepared with a Smut Fungus Index and a Host Plant Index, with the types and numbers of exsiccata. Below, the list of the 1250 numbers of smut fungi is presented, with their host plants, numbers of exsiccata and types indicated. The smut fungus names are given according to the latest stage of their taxonomy and nomenclature. This,

together with the corrections, makes it possible to bring the names of the distributed specimens to the present level of our knowledge of these fungi.

A few old and new fascicles of the exsiccata are still available at request from H.U.V.

Vánky, Ustilaginales exsiccata no. 1-1250 Smut fungus – host index

Anthracoidea

- A. altiphila* Vánky & M. Piepenbr. – *Carex jamesonii* (901) **isotype**; *C. pichinchensis* (902) **isoparatype**
- A. americana* (Nannf. & B. Lindeb.) Kukkonen – *Carex rostrata* (651)
- A. arenaria* (Syd.) Nannf. – *Carex arenaria* (201, 326, 376, 551, 652); *C. brizoides* (202, 501); *C. colchica* (451); *C. ligerica* (251); *C. praecox* (203)
- A. aspera* (Liro) Kukkonen – *Carex chordorrhiza* (204)
- A. atratae* (Savile) Kukkonen – *Carex heteroneura* (653)
- A. baldensis* Vánky – *Carex baldensis* (452) **topotype**
- A. bigelowii* Nannf. – *Carex bigelowii* (252, 453)
- A. blanda* Vánky & H. Alexander (in press) – *Carex blanda* (1249) **isotype**
- A. buxbaumii* Kukkonen – *Carex buxbaumii* (205, 377, 726); *C. buxbaumii* subsp. *alpina* (253)
- A. capillaris* Kukkonen – *Carex capillaris* (801)
- A. caricis* (Pers.) Bref. – *Carex amguensis* (654)
- A. caricis-albae* (Syd.) Kukkonen – *Carex alba* (254, 255, 327)
- A. carphae* (Speg.) Vánky – *Carpha alpina* (727, 802)
- A. caryophylleae* Kukkonen – *Carex caryophyllea* (206, 655); *C. depressa* subsp. *transsilvanica* (454)
- A. curvulae* Vánky & Kukkonen – *Carex curvula* (378) **isotype**
- A. echinospora* (Lehtola) Kukkonen – *Carex acuta* (256, 328, 552)
- A. elynae* (Syd.) Kukkonen – *Kobresia myosuroides* (803)
- A. fischeri* (P. Karst.) Kukkonen – *Carex canescens* × *mackenziei* (379); *C. curta* × *lapponica* (380); *C. disticha* (329)
- A. globularis* Kukkonen – *Carex globularis* (257)
- A. heterospora* (B. Lindeb.) Kukkonen – *Carex aquatilis* (207, 553); *C. elata* subsp. *omskiana* (502); *C. gaudichaudiana* (1072); *C. geminata* (1073); *C. lessoniana* (1074); *C. nigra* (208, 258, 381); *C. nigra* var. *juncea* (728)
- A. hostianae* B. Lindeb. ex Nannf. – *Carex hostiana* (259)
- A. humilis* Vánky – *Carex humilis* (22 **isotype**, 601, 656)
- A. inclusa* Bref. – *Carex rostrata* (209, 382, 729, 804)
- A. intercedens* Nannf. – *Carex lasiocarpa* (260)
- A. irregularis* (Liro) Boidol & Poelt – *Carex digitata* f. *intermedia* (210); *C. digitata* × *ornithopoda* (657); *C. ornithopoda* (211, 455); *C. pediformis* (456, 658)
- A. kariii* (Liro) Nannf. – *Carex brunnescens* (330); *C. canescens* (262); *C. davalliana* (263); *C. dioica* (212, 331); *C. echinata* (213, 264, 383, 730)

- A. lasiocarpae* B. Lindeb. ex Kukkonen – *Carex lasiocarpa* (214)
- A. limosa* (Syd.) Kukkonen – *Carex limosa* (215, 384, 385); *C. limosa* × *rariflora* (731)
- A. lindebergiae* (Kukkonen) Kukkonen – *Kobresia simpliciuscula* (216)
- A. michelii* Vánky – *Carex michelii* (332, 554)
- A. paniceae* Kukkonen – *Carex livida* (217, 386); *C. panicea* (218, 503, 659, 660); *C. vaginata* (265, 333)
- A. pannucea* (805) = *A. uleana*
- A. pilosae* Vánky – *Carex pilosa* (387, 661)
- A. pratensis* (Syd.) Boidol & Poelt – *Carex flacca* (555, 662, 806)
- A. pseudirregularis* U. Braun – *Carex pallescens* (663)
- A. rupestris* Kukkonen – *Carex rupestris* (388, 807)
- A. schoenus* (G. Cunn.) Vánky – *Schoenus pauciflorus* (457, 732)
- A. scirpi* (J.G. Kühn) Kukkonen – *Scirpus cespitosus* (266, 267, 334)
- A. sclerotiformis* (Cooke & Masee) Kukkonen – *Uncinia laxiflora* (556); *U. leptostachya* (335); *U. rubra* (733); *U. uncinata* (336)
- A. sempervirentis* Vánky – *Carex ferruginea* (557, 734); *C. firma* (268, 558, 602); *C. kitaibeliana* (808); *C. mucronata* (735); *C. sempervirens* (269, 270, 458, 664)
- A. subinclusa* (Körn.) Bref. – *Carex acutiformis* (389); *C. hirta* (459); *C. riparia* (219, 390); *C. vesicaria* (220, 391)
- A. tomentosae* Vánky – *Carex tomentosa* (261 **isotype**, 460, 665)
- A. turfosa* (Syd.) Kukkonen – *Carex dioica* (221)
- A. uleana* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Carex bonplandii* (805)
- A. unciniae* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Uncinia hamata* (903) **isotype**

Aurantiosporium

- A. marisci* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Mariscus thunbergii* (1001) **isotype**
- A. scleriae* Vánky – *Scleria flexuosa* (1132) **isotype**
- A. subnitens* (J. Schröt. & Henn.) M. Piepenbr. & Vánky & Oberwinkler – *Scleria melaleuca* (896)

Bauerago

- B. abstrusa* (Malençon) Vánky – *Juncus gregiflorus* (1002)
- B. commelinae* (Komarov) Denchev – *Commelina communis* (539, 635, 871)
- B. gardneri* (McKenzie & Vánky) Vánky – *Cyperus ustulatus* (873)

Burrillia

- B. ajrekari* Thirum. – *Monochoria vaginalis* var. *pauciflora* (504)
- B. sagittariae* (1003) = *Pseudodermatosorus sagittariae*

Cintractia

- C. amazonica* Syd. & P. Syd. – *Rhynchospora heterochaeta* & *R. leae* (1101)

- C. axicola* (951) = *C. mitchellii*
C. axicola (Berk.) Cornu – *Cyperus compressus* (271, 811); *C. rotundus* (272, 812); *Fimbristylis dichotoma* (505, 809); *F. diphylla* (337)
C. caricis (22) = *Anthracoidea humilis*
C. leucoderma (810) = *Leucocintractia scleriae*
C. limitata G.P. Clinton – *Cyperus articulatus* (1004); *C. cyperoides* subsp. *pseudoflavus* (1071); *C. ligularis* (904); *Kyllinga polyphylla* (952)
C. lipocarphae Vánky, C. Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Bulbostylis barbata* (1241), *Lipocarpha microcephala* (1086) **isotype**
C. mitchellii Vánky – *Fimbristylis dichotoma* (1243); *F. ovata* (1186); *F. tetragona* (951)
C. oreoboli Vánky & McKenzie – *Oreobolus strictus* (736) **isotype**
C. peribebyensis (271, 272, 811, 812) = *C. axicola*
C. solida (Berk.) M. Piepenbr. – *Schoenus apogon* (753)
C. spadicea (273) = *Stegocintractia spadicea*
C. utriculicola (813) = *Trichocintractia utriculicola*
- Conidiosporomyces**
C. ayresii (Berk.) Vánky – *Panicum maximum* (186, 691, 762, 814); *Setaria sphacelata* (1244)
C. verruculosus (Wakef.) Vánky – *Setaria pallide-fusca* (1115); *S. sphacelata* (1116)
- Dermatosorus**
D. cyperi Vánky – *Cyperus* aff. *celluloso-reticulatus* (905) **isotype**
- Doassansia**
D. alismatis (Nees) Cornu – *Alisma plantago-aquatica* (126)
D. alismatis-oligococci (176) = *Pseudodermatosorus alismatis-oligococci*
D. epilobii Farl. – *Epilobium alpestre* & *E. alsinifolium* (666); *E. hornemannii* (737)
D. hottoniae (222) = *Heterodoassansia hottoniae*
D. hydrophila (64) = *Doassansiopsis hydrophila*
D. hygrophilae Thirum. (815) = *Heterodoassansia hygrophilae*
D. sagittariae (Fueckel) C. Fisch – *Sagittaria sagittifolia* (74, 128, 274)
- Doassansiopsis**
D. hydrophila (A. Dietr.) Lavrov – *Potamogeton lucens* (64); *P. natans* (16, 127, 223)
D. limnocharidis (Cif.) Vánky – *Limnocharis flava* (816)
D. nymphoides Vánky – *Nymphoides rautanenii* (1126) **isotype**
- Doassinga**
D. callitrichis (Liro) Vánky, R. Bauer & Begerow – *Callitriche stagnalis* (339, 560)
- Eballistra**
E. brachiariae (Viégas) R. Bauer, Begerow, A. Nagler & Oberw. – *Brachiaria distachya* (282, 911); *B. piligera* (1011); *Urochloa trichopus* (1070)
E. lineata (Cooke) R. Bauer, Begerow, A. Nagler & Oberw. – *Zizania aquatica* var. *angustifolia* (741)
E. oryzae (Syd. & P. Syd.) R. Bauer, Begerow, A. Nagler & Oberw. – *Oryza sativa* (910)
- Entorrhiza**
E. aschersoniana (Magnus) Lagerh. – *Juncus bufonius* (19, 559, 817)
E. caspariana (Magnus) Lagerh. – *Juncus articulatus* (129, 818)
E. cypericola (Magnus) C. Weber – *Cyperus flavescens* (47)
E. digitata (129) = *E. caspariana*
E. fineranae Vánky – *Eleocharis geniculata* (*Scirpus geniculatus*) (906)
- Entyloma**
E. achilleae Magnus – *Achillea millefolium* (75)
E. arnicale Ellis & Everh. – *Arnica montana* (392); *A. mollis* (667)
E. atlanticum Massenot – *Geranium tuberosum* (738)
E. australe Speg. – *Physalis peruviana* (819)
E. bellidistri Maire – *Aster bellidistri* (668)
E. bellidis K. Krieg. – *Bellis perennis* (1005)
E. bidentis Henn. – *Bidens pilosa* (177, 509, 564, 822)
E. calceolariae Lagerh. – *Calceolaria chelidonioides* (907); *C. tripartita* (908)
E. calendulae (Oudem.) de Bary – *Calendula officinalis* (18, 115, 338, 669)
E. callitrichis (339, 560) = *Doassinga callitrichis*
E. chrysosplenii J. Schröt. – *Chrysosplenium alternifolium* (33, 340, 603)
E. compositarum (44) = *E. gaillardianum*
E. corydalis de Bary – *Corydalis bulbosa* (670)
E. dactylidis (49, 85, 561, 739) = *Jamesdicksonia dactylidis*, s. lat.
E. dactylidis (51) = *Jamesdicksonia irregularis*
E. dahliae Syd. & P. Syd. – *Dahlia coccinea* (1076); *D. pinnata* (820); *D. variabilis* (104, 178, 461, 506)
E. eryngii (Corda) de Bary – *Eryngium campestre* (25, 130)
E. eryngii-dichotomi Maire – *Eryngium creticum* (393)
E. eryngii-plani Cif. – *Eryngium planum* (71, 507)
E. eschscholtziae Harkn. – *Eschscholtzia californica* (1077)
E. fergussonii (Berk. & Broome) Plowr. – *Myosotis laxa* subsp. *caespitosa* (131); *M. scorpioides* (275, 341, 562, 604)
E. ficariae Thum. ex A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Ranunculus ficaria* (45, 132, 179, 342, 394, 606, 740, 821); *R. f.* subsp. *bulbifer* (395)
E. ficariae (87, 102, 103, 276, 277, 396, 508, 563, 605) = *E. ranunculi-repentis*
E. frondosa Vánky – *Bidens frondosa* (1142) **isotype**
E. fumariae J. Schröt. – *Fumaria rostellata* (89)
E. fuscum J. Schröt. – *Glaucium flavum* (278)
E. gaillardianum Vánky – *Gaillardia aristata* (44) **isotype**; *G. pulchella* (397)
E. galinsogae Syd. & P. Syd. – *Galinsoga parviflora* (909)
E. glaucii (278) = *E. fuscum*

- E. guaraniticum* Speg. – *Bidens bipinnata* (1067); *B. pilosa* var. *radiata* (1058)
E. guaraniticum (177, 509, 564, 822) = *E. bidentis*
E. helosciadii Magnus – *Oenanthe silaifolia* (1181)
E. hieracii Syd. & P. Syd. ex Cif. – *Hieracium transsilvanicum* (73); *H. vulgatum* (72)
E. holwayi P. Syd. – *Cosmos caudatus* (1203); *C. sulphureus* (1204)
E. jaegeriae Syd. – *Jaegeria hirta* (953)
E. leontices Sävil. – *Leontice albertii* (565)
E. linariae J. Schröt. – *Linaria vulgaris* (40, 566, 671, 823)
E. lineatum (741) = *Eballistra lineata*
E. madae Cif. – *Madia gracilis* (742)
E. magnusii (Ule) Woronin – *Gnaphalium uliginosum* (343)
E. magocyanum Bubák – *Tordylium maximum* (83) **topotype**
E. matricariae Rostr. – *Leucanthemopsis alpina* (279); *Matricaria perforata* (23, 280 **topotype**, 344, 607)
E. microsporium (Unger) J. Schröt. – *Ranunculus muricatus* (824); *R. pilosus* (825); *R. repens* (63, 462, 826); *R. sieboldii* (672)
E. novae-zelandiae McKenzie & Vánky – *Hydrocotyle heteromeria* (1051)
E. oryzae (910) = *Eballistra oryzae*
E. picridis Rostr. – *Picris hieracioides* (224)
E. polysporum (Peck) Farl. – *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* (567)
E. ranunculi-repentis Sternon – *Ranunculus acris* (276, 605); *R. auricomus* (87, 508); *R. cassubicus* (102); *R. polyanthemos* (277); *R. repens* (396, 563); *R. sceleratus* (103)
E. saccardianum Scalia ex Cif. – *Senecio minimus* (954)
E. serotinum J. Schröt. – *Borago officinalis* (345, 608); *Symphytum officinale* (2)
E. siegesbeckiae Vánky – *Siegesbeckia orientalis* (1205) **isotype**
E. spegazzinii Sacc. & P. Syd. – *Bidens pilosa* (1193)
E. zinniae Syd. – *Zinnia pauciflora* (1006) **topotype**

Erratomyces

- E. patelii* (Pavgi & Thirum.) M. Piepenbr. & R. Bauer – *Vigna mungo* (1052); *V. unguiculata* (1102)

Farysia

- F. butleri* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Syd. & P. Syd. – *Carex echinochloa* (180, 346, 1165)
F. caricis-filicinae (180, 346) = *F. butleri*
F. chardoniana Zundel – *Carex polystachya* (827)
F. corniculata Vánky – *Carex lemmanniana* (955) **topotype**
F. endotricha (568, 743, 828) = *Farysporium endotrichum*
F. merrillii (Henn.) Syd. & P. Syd. – *Carex virgata* (829)
F. nakanishikii (Henn.) Syd. & P. Syd. – *Carex brunnea* (956)
F. thuemenii (A.A. Fisch. Waldh.) Nannf. – *Carex baccans* (151); *C. lessoniana* (1155); *C. maorica* (744); *C. polysticha* (1103); *C. riparia* (26, 281, 347, 609, 745, 746); *C. tweediana* (1104)

Farysporium

- F. endotrichum* (Berk.) Vánky – *Gahnia procera* (743); *G. setifolia* (568); *G. xanthocarpa* (828)

Fulvisporium

- F. restifaciens* (D.E. Shaw) Vánky – *Stipa stuposa* (414)

Gjaerumia

- G. ossifragi* (Rostr.) R. Bauer, M. Lutz & Oberw. – *Narthecium ossifragum* (1187)

Glomosporium

- G. amaranthi* (24, 510) = *Thecaphora amaranthi*
G. leptideum (Syd.) Kochman – *Chenopodium album* (398)

Heterodoassansia

- H. hottoniae* (Rostr.) Vánky – *Hottonia palustris* (222)
H. hygrophilae (Thirum.) Vánky (in press) – *Hygrophila spinosa* (815)

Heterotolyposporium

- H. lepidospermae* Vánky – *Lepidosperma ensiforme* (957) **isotype**
H. piluliforme (Berk.) Vánky – *Juncus* cf. *caespitosus* (840); *J. planifolius* (958)

Ingoldiomyces

- I. hyalosporus* (Masse) Vánky – *Nassella mexicana* (930)

Jamesdicksonia

- J. brunkii* (Ellis & Galloway) J. Walker & R.G. Shivas – *Andropogon saccharoides* (1206)
J. festucae Vánky – *Festuca toluensis* (1207) **isotype**
J. dactylidis (Pass.) R. Bauer, Begerow, A. Nagler & Oberw. – *Agrostis alba* (49); *A. stolonifera* (739); *Alopecurus pratensis* (561); *Deschampsia cespitosa* (85)
J. irregularis (Johanson) R. Bauer, Begerow, A. Nagler & Oberw. – *Poa annua* (51)

Leucocintractia

- L. scleriae* (DC.) M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw. – *Rhynchospora corymbosa* (810)

Liroa

- L. emodensis* (Berk.) Cif. – *Polygonum chinense* (181, 399, 569)

Lundquistia

- L. dieteliana* (Henn.) Vánky – *Tripsacum dactyloides* (1201)
L. mexicana Vánky – *Andropogon gerardii* (1202) **isotype**
L. panici-leucophaei (Bref.) Vánky – *Panicum elephantipes* (1117)
L. ugandensis (Henn.) Vánky – *Digitaria abyssinica* (1172)

Macalpinomyces

- M. bursus* (Berk.) Vánky – *Themeda quadrivalvis* (844)
M. chrysopogonicola (Mundk. & Thirum.) Vánky – *Chrysopogon fulvus* (959)
M. chrysopogonis (959) = *M. chrysopogonicola*

- M. eragrostiellae* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Eragrostiella bifaria* (960) **isotype**
- M. eriachnis* (Thum.) Langdon & Full. – *Eriachne aristidea* (1007); *E. capillaris* (1091); *E. dominii* (1105); *E. helmsii* (1096); *E. sulcata* (961)
- M. ewartii* (McAlpine) Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Sorghum stipoideum* (1094)
- M. leptocarydionis* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Leptocarydion vulpiastrum* (1137) **isotype**
- M. loudetiae* (Vienn.-Bourg.) Vánky – *Loudetia flavida* (1008)
- M. magicus* Vánky & T. Vánky – *Loudetia flava* (1130) **isotype**
- M. neglectus* (Niessl) Vánky – *Setaria glauca* (43, 169, 410, 523, 689); *S. viridis* (524)
- M. nodiglumis* Vánky – *Tristachya nodiglumis* (1139) **isotype**
- M. ovaricolopsis* (Vánky) Vánky – *Andropogon gayanus* (1135)
- M. panic* Vánky (in press) – *Panicum aequinerve* (1237) **isotype**
- M. pogonarthriae* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Pogonarthria squarrosa* (1131) **isotype**
- M. pretoriensis* (Pole-Evans) Vánky – *Panicum maximum* (1143); *Urochloa panicoides* (1027)
- M. simplex* Vánky – *Loudetia simplex* (1064) **isotype**
- M. spermophorus* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis ex de Toni) Vánky – *Eragrostis cilianensis* (1208); *E. ferruginea* (546); *E. minor* (14, 547); *E. pilosa* (893); *Sporobolus australasicus* (1050, 1111)
- M. trichopterygis* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Trichopteryx dregeana* (1009) **isotype**
- M. tripogonis* (M.S. Patil) Vánky – *Tripogon jacquemontii* (857)
- M. tristachyae* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Tristachya leucothrix* (1010) **isotype**
- M. tuberculatus* Vánky – *Bouteloua curtipendula* (1209) **isotype**
- M. ugandensis* Vánky – *Sorghastrum stipoides* (1177) **isotype**
- M. zonotriches* Vánky – *Zonotriche inamoena* (1133)

Melaniella

- M. oreophila* (Syd.) R. Bauer, Vánky, Begerow & Oberw. – *Selaginella abyssinica* (1060); *S. delicatula* (912) **isoneotype**

Melanopsichium

- M. pennsylvanicum* Hirschh. – *Polygonum glabrum* (1081); *P. lapathifolium* (463, 673); *P. senegalense* (225)

Melanotaenium

- M. ari* (69, 226, 348, 464) = *Melanustilospora ari*
- M. brachiariae* (282, 911, 1011) = *Eballistra brachiariae*
- M. endogenum* (Unger) De Bary – *Galium mollugo* (610)
- M. euphorbiae* (Lenz) M.D. Whitehead & Thirum. – *Euphorbia heterophylla* (962)
- M. indicum* (1012) = *Phragmotenium indicum*
- M. oreophilum* (912) = *Melaniella oreophila*

Melanustilospora

- M. ari* (Cooke) Denchev – *Arum maculatum* (226, 464); *A. orientale* (69, 348)

Microbotryum

- M. anomalum* (J. Kunze ex G. Winter) Vánky – *Bilderdykia aubertii* (482); *B. convolvulus* (53, 140, 699); *B. dumetorum* (365, 419)
- M. betonicae* (Beck) R. Bauer & Oberw. – *Salvia pratensis* (631)
- M. bistortarum* (DC.) Vánky – *Polygonum bistorta* (776); *P. viviparum* (141, 357, 421, 483, 537, 701, 868)
- M. bosniacum* (Beck) Vánky – *Polygonum alpinum* (632)
- M. cordae* (Liro) G. Deml & Prillinger – *Polygonum hydropiper* (52, 162, 488, 703); *P. posumbu* (934)
- M. debiscens* (L. Ling) Vánky – *Polygonum amplexicaule* (936)
- M. dianthorum* (Liro) H. Scholz & I. Scholz – *Dianthus carthusianorum* (77, 446, 511, 570); *D. deltooides* (512)
- M. duriaeanum* (Tul. & C. Tul.) Vánky – *Cerastium brachypetalum* (112)
- M. holostei* (de Bary) Vánky – *Holosteum umbellatum* (91)
- M. intermedium* (J. Schröt.) Vánky – *Scabiosa columbaria* (592); *S. lucida* (880); *S. ochroleuca* (100); *S. triandra* (315)
- M. longisetum* (Vánky & Oberw.) Vánky – *Polygonum longisetum* (786) **isotype**
- M. lychnidis-dioicae* (DC. ex Liro) G. Deml & Oberw. – *Silene alba* (116, 249, 448, 467, 571, 747); *S. dioica* (148, 375, 449, 613, 674, 675)
- M. majus* (J. Schröt.) G. Deml & Oberw. – *Silene otites* (12, 168)
- M. marginale* (DC.) Vánky – *Polygonum bistorta* (317, 435, 708)
- M. moenchiae-manticae* (Lindtner) Vánky – *Moenchia mantica* (82)
- M. nepalense* (Liro) Vánky – *Polygonum alatum* (787, 941)
- M. onopordi* (Vánky) Vánky – *Onopordum bracteatum* (882) **isotype**
- M. parlatoarei* (A.A. Fisch. Waldh.) Vánky – *Rumex maritimus* (1248)
- M. piperi* (G.P. Clinton) Vánky – *Polygonum alatum* (943); *P. alpinum* (641)
- M. pustulatum* (DC.) R. Bauer & Oberw. – *Polygonum bistorta* (11, 642, 713, 791); *P. viviparum* (714)
- M. reticulatum* (Liro) R. Bauer & Oberw. – *Polygonum lapathifolium* (42, 199, 440, 545, 594, 715, 716); *P. pennsylvanicum* (792); *P. senegalense* (244)
- M. scabiosae* Vánky – *Knautia arvensis* (95, 170, 245, 596, 885)
- M. scolymi* (Juel) Vánky – *Scolymus hispanicus* (1200)
- M. scorzonerae* (Alb. & Schwein.) G. Deml & Prillinger – *Scorzonera hispanica* (644); *S. humilis* (890); *S. purpurea* (793)
- M. shastense* (Zundel) Vánky – *Polygonum shastense* (717) **topotype**

- M. silenes-inflatae* (DC. ex Liro) G. Deml & Oberw. – *Lychnis viscaria* (830); *Silene vulgaris* (10, 117, 250); *Viscaria vulgaris* (119, 149)
- M. silybum* Vánky & Berner – *Silybum marianum* (1188 isotype, 1188B topotype)
- M. stellariae* (Liro) G. Deml & Oberw. – *Myosoton aquaticum* (322, 323, 612); *Stellaria graminea* (54, 150); *S. holostea* (614)
- M. stygium* (Liro) Vánky – *Rumex acetosa* (720, 721)
- M. succisae* (Magnus) R. Bauer & Oberw. – *Succisa pratensis* (599, 722)
- M. tenuisporum* (Cif.) Vánky – *Polygonum barbatum* (947); *P. glabrum* (1013); *P. punctatum* (723)
- M. tragopogonis-pratensis* (Pers.) R. Bauer & Oberw. – *Tragopogon pratensis* (174, 319, 444, 647, 724); *Tragopogon pratensis* subsp. *orientalis* (17, 371)
- M. tuberculiforme* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Polygonum runcinatum* (799)
- M. vinosum* (Tul. & C. Tul.) Denchev – *Oxyria digyna* (29, 321, 446)
- M. violaceum* (511, 512, 570) = *M. dianthorum*
- M. violaceum* (Pers. : Pers.) G. Deml & Oberw. – *Dianthus amurensis* (373); *D. lumnitzeri* (611); *D. microlepis* (831); *D. pavonius* (465); *D. petraeus* (374); *D. pontederiae* (118); *D. taiwanensis* (832); *D. tenuifolius* (147); *Gypsophila repens* (676); *Saponaria ocyroides* (748); *S. officinalis* (120, 447, 513, 677, 678); *S. pumilio* (466); *Silene acaulis* (514, 679); *S. nutans* (515)
- M. violaceum* (467, 571, 613) = *M. lychnidis-dioicae*
- M. violaceum* (612, 614) = *M. stellariae*
- M. violaceum* var. *stellariae* (54, 150) = *M. stellariae*
- M. warmingii* (Rostr.) Vánky – *Rumex domesticus* (200)
- Moesziomyces**
- M. bullatus* (J. Schröt.) Vánky – *Echinochloa crus-galli* (35, 283, 516, 572); *Leersia hexandra* (517); *Paspalum distichum* (833); *Pennisetum americanum* (154)
- M. eriocauli* (G.P. Clinton) Vánky – *Eriocaulon cinereum* (913)
- Moreaua**
- M. aterrima* (Tul. & C. Tul.) Vánky – *Carex caryophyllea* (6, 185); *C. halleriana* (293)
- M. caustidis* (Vánky) Vánky – *Caustis flexuosa* (978)
- M. cyatochaetae* (Websdane & Vánky) Vánky – *Cyatochaeta avenacea* (979)
- M. evandrae* (Websdane & Vánky) Vánky – *Evandra aristata* (980) isotype
- M. fimbriatylidis* Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Fimbristylis dichotoma* (1085) isotype
- M. gabniae* (Vánky & C. Vánky) Vánky – *Gabnia radula* (981) isotype
- M. gymnoschoeni* (Vánky & C. Vánky) Vánky – *Gymnoschoenus anceps* (1036) isoparatype; *G. sphaerocephalus* (982) isotype
- M. kochiana* (Gäum.) Vánky – *Schoenus nigricans* (861); *S. nigricans* × *ferrugineus* (189) topotype
- M. lepidospermae* (McAlpine) Vánky – *Lepidosperma angustatum* (1037); *L. gunnii* (983)
- M. littoralis* (G. Cunn.) Vánky – *Baumea juncea* (768)
- M. mauritiana* (Syd.) Vánky – *Fimbristylis ovata* (984)
- M. megaglomerulosa* (Vánky) Vánky – *Lepidosperma filiforme* (1038) isoparatype; *L. gunnii* (985) isotype
- M. mesomelaenae* (Websdane & Vánky) Vánky – *Mesomelaena pseudostygia* (1124)
- M. muelleriana* (Thum.) Vánky – *Gabnia trifida* (986)
- M. rhynchosporae-cephalotis* (Vánky & T. Vánky) Vánky – *Rhynchospora cephaloides* (862) isotype
- M. rodwayi* (McAlpine) Vánky – *Lepidosperma effusum* (987); *L. gladiatum* (988); *L. gunnii* (989)
- M. schoeni* (Vánky & McKenzie) Vánky – *Schoenus brevifolius* (990) isotype
- M. tetrairie* (Vánky) Vánky – *Tetralia capillaris* (991) isotype
- Mundkurella**
- M. mossii* Savile – *Aralia nudicaulis* (834)
- M. schefflerae* Vánky, C. Vánky & McKenzie – *Schefflera digitata* (1014) isotype
- Mycosyrinx**
- M. cissi* (DC.) Beck – *Cissus sicyoides* (835)
- Nannfeldtiomyces**
- N. anomalus* (Crowell) Vánky – *Sparganium minimum* (349)
- N. sparganii* (Lagerh.) Vánky – *Sparganium erectum* (350, 400, 680)
- Neovossia**
- N. barclayana* (518, 836) = *Tilletia barclayana*
- N. molinae* (Thum.) Körn. – *Phragmites australis* (573, 615)
- N. opaca* (837) = *Tilletia opaca*
- N. sumatii* (838) = *Tilletia sumatii*
- Oberwinkleria**
- O. annulata* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Ortache erectifolia* (914) isotype
- Orphanomyces**
- O. arcticus* (Rostr.) Savile – *Carex brunnescens* (574); *C. duriuscula* (681)
- O. hungaricus* Vánky & J. Gönczöl – *Carex acuta* (284 isotype, 401)
- O. vankyi* Savile – *Carex acutiformis* (175) isotype
- Pericladium**
- P. grewiae* Pass. – *Grewia villosa* (351)
- Phragmotaeonium**
- P. indicum* (Vánky, M.S. Patil & N.D. Sharma) R. Bauer, Begerow, A. Nagler & Oberw. – *Ischaemum indicum* (1012) isoparatype

Pseudodermatosorus

- P. alismatis-oligococci* (Vánky) Vánky – *Alisma oligococcum* (176) **isotype**; *Lymnophyton obtusifolium* (1061)
P. sagittariae (Vánky & C. Vánky) Vánky – *Sagittaria planitiana* (1003) **isotype**

Pseudodoassansia

- P. hydrocleidis* Vánky – *Hydrocleis nymphoides* (1079) **isotype**

Restiosporium

- R. baloskionis* Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Baloskion tetrphyllum* (1141) **isotype**
R. dapsilanthi Vánky – *Dapsilanthus elatior* (1149) **isotype**
R. meneyae Vánky – *Lyginia barbata* (1075) **isotype**
R. restionum (Nees) Vánky – *Chordifex microcodon* (1247)

Rhamphospora

- R. nymphaeae* D.D. Cunn. – *Nymphaea alba* (519, 575); *N. alba* × *mexicana* (749); *N. stellata* (182); *N. tetragona* (682)

Schizonella

- S. cocconii* (Morini) Liro – *Carex flacca* (152, 683); *C. halleriana* (285, 684); *C. humilis* (109)
S. intercedens Vánky & A. Nagler – *Carex michelii* (108, 353, 1015) **isotype**
S. melanogramma (DC.) J. Schröt. – *Carex brevicollis* (81); *C. digitata* (402); *C. firma* (576); *C. fuliginosa* (352); *C. ornithopoda* (403); *C. pilulifera* (839); *C. sempervirens* (468)

Schroeteria (= Ascomycota)

- S. bornmuelleri* Magnus – *Veronica rubrifolia* (750) (ascomycete)
S. decaisneana (Boud.) de Toni – *Veronica hederifolia* (27, 227) (ascomycete)
S. delastrina (Tul. & C. Tul.) G. Winter – *Veronica arvensis* (9, 685) (ascomycete)

Sorosporium

- S. catharticum* (183) = *Sporisorium penniseti*
S. cenchri (228) = *Sporisorium cenchri*
S. flagellatum (229) = *Sporisorium flagellatum*
S. formosanum (184) = *Sporisorium formosanum*
S. healdii (354) = *Sporisorium themedae-cymbariae*
S. holci-sorghii (286) = *Sporisorium reilianum*
S. neillii (1016) = *Tolyposporium neillii*
S. piluliforme (840) = *Heterotolyposporium piluliforme*
S. saponariae (55, 121, 122, 123, 230, 287, 288, 355, 404, 405, 469, 577, 616, 752) = *Thecaphora saponariae*
S. solidum (753) = *Cintractia solida*
S. tumefaciens (231) = *Sporisorium tumefaciens*

Sphacelotheca

- S. andropogonis* (30, 232, 233, 289) = *Sporisorium andropogonis*
S. andropogonis (234) = *Sporisorium vanderystii*

- S. hydropiperis* (Schumach.) de Bary – *Polygonum hydropiper* (56, 520, 578, 617); *P. minus* (124); *P. mite* (432, 490); *P. longisetum* (618); *P. persicaria* (754); *P. posumbu* var. *laxiflorum* (521); *P. thunbergii* (686)

- S. hydropiperis* (Schumach.) de Bary var. *koordersiana* (Bref.) Denchev & Kakish. – *Polygonum punctatum* (915); *P. salicifolium* (755)

- S. koordersiana* (915, 755) = *S. hydropiperis* var. *koordersiana*
S. schweinfurthiana (356) = *Sporisorium schweinfurthianum*
S. sorghi (50) = *Sporisorium sorghi*
S. spermophora (14) = *Macalpinomyces spermophorus*
S. ustilaginea (357) = *Microbotryum bistortarum*

Sporisorium

- S. absconditum* Vánky – *Schizachyrium fragile* (1167) **isotype**; *S. sanguineum* (1239)
S. aegyptiacum (A.A. Fisch. Waldh.) Vánky – *Schismus arabicus* (756); *S. barbatus* (1146)
S. africanum (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Brachiaria serrata* (1028)
S. amaurae Vánky & C. Vánky – *Polytrias amaura* (963) **isotype**
S. andropogonis (406) = *S. vanderystii*
S. andropogonis (Opiz) Vánky – *Andropogon perforatus* (1210); *A. tectorum* (233); *A. saccharoides* (964, 1211); *Dichanthium ischaemum* (30, 232, 470, 841); *Heteropogon contortus* (289)
S. andropogonis (1230) = *S. doidgeae*
S. andropogonis-aciculati (Petch) Vánky – *Chrysopogon aciculatus* (522)
S. anthistiriae (Cobb) Vánky – *Themeda triandra* (579)
S. apludae (Syd. & P. Syd.) L. Guo – *Apluda mutica* (1017)
S. apludae-aristatae (B.V. Patil & Thirum.) Vánky – *Apluda mutica* (916)
S. aristidicola (Speg.) Vánky – *Aristida adscensionis* (918, 1154); *A. hintonii* (1212); *A. redacta* (1113); *A. ternipes* (1213); *Aristida* sp. (1120)
S. aristidicola (1119) = *S. consanguineum*
S. arthraxonis (842, 843) = *S. tranzschelianum*
S. arundinellae (917) = *S. arundinellae-pumilae*
S. arundinellae-pumilae Vánky – *Arundinella pumila* (917) **isotype**
S. australasiaticum Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Sorghum nitidum* (1123) **isotype**
S. bonariense (1117) = *Lundquistia panici-leucophaei*
S. bothriochloae (L. Ling) Vánky – *Dichanthium fecundum* (1196); *D. sericeum* subsp. *polystachyum* (1199)
S. bursum (844) = *Macalpinomyces bursus*
S. caledonicum (Pat.) Vánky – *Heteropogon contortus* (1053)
S. capillipedii (1054) = *S. doidgeae*
S. catharticum (845) = *S. penniseti*
S. cenchri (Lagerh.) Vánky – *Cenchrus pauciflorus* (228, 1214)
S. chrysopogonis Vánky – *Chrysopogon fulvus* (407) **isotype**
S. congensis (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Hyparrhenia diplandra* (1179)
S. consanguineum (918) = *S. aristidicola*

- S. consanguineum* (Ellis & Everh.) Vánky – *Aristida benthamii* (1018); *A. jerichoensis* (1119); *A. junciformis* (1057); *A. uruguayensis* (1106)
- S. cornutum* (Syd., P. Syd. & E.J. Butler) Vánky – *Ophiurus exaltatus* (846)
- S. cruentum* (J.G. Kühn) Vánky – *Sorghum halepense* (408, 471, 687)
- S. cryptum* (McAlpine) Vánky – *Brachiaria holosericea* (1185)
- S. culmiperdum* (J. Schröt.) Vánky – *Andropogon bicornis* (847)
- S. cymbicum* Vánky – *Cymbopogon nardus* (1150) **isotype**; *C. plurinodis* (1156) **paratype**; *C. validus* (1151) **paratype**
- S. dacryoideum* Vánky – *Aristida adscensionis* (1215) **isotype**
- S. destruens* (Schltdl.) Vánky – *Panicum miliaceum* (472)
- S. dimeriae-ornithopoda* Vánky & C. Menge – *Dimeria ornithopoda* (848) **isotype**; *D. o.* var. *khasiana* (1118)
- S. dinteri* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Bothriochloa bladhii* (1194)
- S. doidgeae* (Zundel) Langdon & Full. – *Bothriochloa bladhii* (1230); *Capillipedium spicigerum* (1054)
- S. dolichosorum* (1172) = *Lundquistia ugandensis*
- S. elionuri* (Henn. & Pole-Evans) Vánky – *Elionurus muticus* (1019)
- S. enteromorphum* (McAlpine) Vánky – *Themeda triandra* (1020)
- S. eriochrysis* Vánky – *Eriochrysis brachypogon* (1178) **isotype**
- S. erythraeense* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Hackelochloa granularis* (849)
- S. exsertum* (McAlpine) L. Guo – *Themeda triandra* (965)
- S. fastigiatum* Vánky – *Andropogon fastigiatus* (1066) **isotype**
- S. flagellatum* (Syd., P. Syd. & E.J. Butler) Vánky – *Ischaemum indicum* (229)
- S. formosanum* (Sawada) Vánky – *Panicum repens* (184, 409, 688)
- S. fraserianum* (Syd.) Vánky – *Aristida leptopoda* (1107)
- S. gayanum* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Andropogon gayanus* (1065) **isotype**
- S. guaraniticum* (Speg.) Vánky – *Schizachyrium condensatum* (1168)
- S. hainanae* (Zundel) L. Guo – *Ischaemum aristatum* (1240)
- S. heteropogonicola* (Mundk. & Thirum.) Vánky – *Heteropogon contortus* (919)
- S. hodsonii* (Zundel) Vánky – *Panicum schinzii* (1236)
- S. holwayi* (G.P. Clinton & Zundel) Vánky – *Andropogon bicornis* (850)
- S. hwangense* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Sporobolus panicoides* (1059) **isotype**
- S. indehiscens* (L. Ling) Vánky – *Themeda* × *intermedia* (1021)
- S. inopinatum* Vánky – *Aristida scabrivalvis* (1108) **isotype**
- S. ischaemicola* (L. Ling) Vánky – *Ischaemum heterotrichum* (1231); *I. ?indicum* (1246)
- S. ischaemoides* (Henn.) Vánky – *Hyparrhenia anamesa* (1162); *H. filipendula* (1163); *Hyparrhenia dissoluta* (1158)
- S. iseilematis-ciliati* Vánky – *Iseilema membranaceum* (1093)
- S. iseilematis-vaginiflori* Vánky – *Iseilema vaginiflorum* (1022) **isotype**
- S. lacrymae-jobi* (Mundk.) Vánky – *Coix lacryma-jobi* (920)
- S. langdonii* Vánky – *Themeda avenacea* (1023)
- S. lanigeri* (Magnus) Vánky – *Cymbopogon flexuosus* (1159); *C. marginatus* (1160); *C. obtectus* (1161)
- S. leelingianum* Vánky – *Hyparrhenia cymbaria* (1180), *H. tamba* (1153)
- S. lepturi* (Thum.) Vánky – *Hemarthria altissima* (757); *H. uncinata* (966)
- S. linderi* (Zundel) Vánky – *Digitaria eriantha* (1026)
- S. lingianum* Vánky – *Anthephora elongata* (1138)
- S. lophopogonis* (Thirum. & Pavgi) Vánky – *Lophopogon tridentatus* (921)
- S. loudetiae-pedicellatae* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Loudetia pedicellata* (1024) **isotype**
- S. manilense* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Sacciolepis indica* (854)
- S. melinis* (Zundel) Vánky – *Melinis nerviglumis* (1025); *M. repens* (1127)
- S. microstegii* (S. Ahmad) L. Guo – *Microstegium ciliatum* (939); *M. nudum* (940)
- S. mishrae* Vánky – *Apluda mutica* (967)
- S. mnesithea* (Mishra) Vánky – *Mnesithea laevis* (1197)
- S. modestum* (Syd.) H. Scholz – *Enneapogon avenaceus* (1089)
- S. monakai* (Mishra) Vánky – *Isachne globosa* (922)
- S. moniliferum* (Ellis & Everh.) L. Guo – *Heteropogon contortus* (851); *H. melanocarpus* (1097)
- S. montaniense* (Ellis & Holway) Vánky – *Eragrostis mexicana* (1216)
- S. mysorensis* (Pavgi & Thirum.) Vánky – *Capillipedium huegelii* (923)
- S. nealii* (Ellis & F.W. Anderson) Vánky – *Heteropogon melanocarpus* (924)
- S. neglectum* (410, 523, 524, 689) = *Macalpinomyces neglectus*
- S. nervosum* Vánky, C. Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Sehima nervosum* (1088) **isotype**
- S. occidentale* (Seym. ex G.P. Clinton) Vánky & Snetselaar – *Andropogon gerardii* (758)
- S. ophiuri* (Henn.) Vánky – *Rottboellia exaltata* (525, 852)
- S. ovarium* (Griffiths) Vánky – *Brachiaria piligera* (1184); *Panicum maximum* (1055); *Urochloa trichopus* (1164)
- S. panici* (1055) = *S. ovarium*
- S. panicicola* Vánky (in press) – *Panicum coloratum* (1238) **isotype**
- S. panici-fasciculati* Vánky (in press) – *Panicum fasciculatum* (1232) **isotype**
- S. panici-hirticaulis* Vánky (in press) – *Panicum hirticaule* (1233) **isotype**
- S. panici-leucophaei* (1117) = *Lundquistia panici-leucophaei*
- S. paspali-thunbergii* (Henn.) Vánky – *Paspalum scrobiculatum* (526, 925); *P. thunbergii* (619)
- S. penniseti* (Rabenh.) Ershad – *Cenchrus ciliaris* (183, 845)
- S. pole-evansii* (1026) **isotype** = *S. linderi*
- S. polliniae* (Magnus) Vánky – *Andropogon distachyos* (690)
- S. pretoriense* (1027, *nom. herb.*) = *Macalpinomyces pretoriensis*
- S. provinciale* (Ellis & Galloway) Vánky & Snetselaar – *Andropogon gerardii* (759)

- S. pseudanthistiriae* (Syd., P. Syd. & E.J. Butler) Vánky – *Pseudanthistiria hispida* (969)
- S. pseudechinolaenae* Vánky & C. Menge – *Pseudechinolaena polystachya* (853) **isotype**
- S. puellare* (620, 621, 760) = *S. vanedrystii*
- S. pulverulentum* (Cooke & Masee) Vánky – *Saccharum strictum* (473)
- S. reilianum* (J.G. Kühn) Langdon & Full. – *Sorghum bicolor* var. *technicum* (286); *S. halepense* (527, 968)
- S. saccolepidis* (854) = *S. manilense*
- S. schizachyrii* Vánky – *Schizachyrium exile* (1128) **isotype**
- S. schweinfurthianum* (Thum.) Vánky – *Imperata cylindrica* (356, 411)
- S. sehimicola* Vánky – *Sehima ischaemoides* (1063) **isotype**
- S. serratum* (1028) = *S. africanum*
- S. setariae* (McAlpine) Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Setaria surgens* (1109)
- S. sorghi* Ehrenb. ex Link – *Sorghum plumosum* (970); *S. bicolor* (50, 172)
- S. spermoideum* (Berk. & Broome) Vánky – *Cymbopogon martinii* (1245)
- S. sphacelatum* Vánky – *Pennisetum sphacelatum* (1145) **isotype**
- S. spodiopogonis* (M.S. Patil) Vánky – *Spodiopogon rhizophorus* (971)
- S. tembuti* (Henn. & Pole-Evans) Vánky, *nom. herb.* (1153) = *S. leelingianum*
- S. tenue* (Syd. & P. Syd.) Vánky – *Bothriochloa macra* (1195)
- S. themedae* (Duke) Vánky – *Themeda quadrivalvis* (926); *T. triandra* (1029)
- S. themedae-arguentis* Vánky – *Themeda arguens* (855) **isotype**; *T. quadrivalvis* (972)
- S. themedae-cymbariae* Vánky – *Themeda cymbaria* (354 **isoparatype**, 973 **isotype**)
- S. tonglinense* (Tracy & Earle) L. Guo – *Ischaemum indicum* (173)
- S. trachypogonis-plumosi* Vánky – *Trachypogon plumosus* (927) **isotype**
- S. transfissum* (Tul. & C. Tul.) G. Deml – *Hyparrhenia hirta* (580)
- S. tranzschelianum* (Lavrov) Karatygin – *Arthraxon hispidus* (842); *A. lanceolatus* (843)
- S. tricholaenae* (Henn.) Vánky – *Tricholaena teneriffae* (856)
- S. tripogonis* (857) **isotype** = *Macalpinomyces tripogonis*
- S. tristachyae-hispidae* (L. Ling) Vánky – *Tristachya leucothrix* (1030)
- S. tristachyae-nodiglumis* Vánky – *Tristachya nodiglumis* (1144) **isotype**
- S. tumefaciens* (McAlpine) Vánky – *Chrysopogon aciculatus* (231); *C. fallax* (1031); *C. latifolius* (974)
- S. ustilaginiforme* Vánky – *Muhlenbergia pulcherrima* (1217) **isotype**
- S. vanderystii* (Henn.) Langdon & Full. – *Exotheca abyssinica* (1171); *Hyparrhenia bracteata* (1169); *H. cymbaria* (1234); *H. diplandra* (1166); *H. hirta* (195, 234, 406, 620, 621, 760); *H. rufa* (1170); *Hyperthelia dissoluta* (1157)
- S. walkeri* Vánky – *Themeda triandra* (975)
- S. wynaadense* (Sundaram) Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Sorghum leiocladum* (1121)
- Stegocintractia**
- S. luzulae* (Sacc.) M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw. – *Luzula luzulina* (60); *L. luzuloides* (144); *L. sudetica* (145)
- S. spadicea* (Liro) M. Piepenbr. & Begerow – *Luzula spadicea* (273)
- Testicularia**
- T. cyperi* Klotzsch – *Rhynchospora careyana* (1032)
- Thecaphora**
- T. affinis* W.G. Schneid. ex A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Astragalus glycyphyllus* (110, 133)
- T. amarantibi* (Hirschh.) Vánky – *Amaranthus hybridus* (1218); *A. retroflexus* (24, 510)
- T. amaranthicola* M. Piepenbr. – *Amaranthus hybridus* (1235)
- T. aterrima* (6, 185) = *Moreaua aterrima*
- T. deformans* (110, 133) = *T. affinis*
- T. saponariae* (F. Rudolphi) Vánky – *Dianthus armeria* (1198); *D. deltoides* (287, 752); *D. pontederiae* (122); *Saponaria officinalis* (230, 288); *Silene alba* (404, 577, 616); *S. italica* (1229); *S. nutans* (405); *S. vulgaris* (123); *Stellaria graminea* (55, 355); *Stellaria holostea* (469); *Tunica saxifraga* (121)
- T. seminis-convolvuli* (Desm.) S. Ito – *Calystegia sepium* (66); *Convolvulus arvensis* (3, 290)
- T. spilanthes* F.O. Freire & Vánky – *Spilanthes oleracea* (976) **isotype**
- T. thlaspeos* (Beck) Vánky – *Arabis hirsuta* (96, 600)
- T. trailii* Cooke – *Cirsium helenioides* (858)
- Tilletia**
- T. anthoxanthi* A. Blytt – *Antoxanthum odoratum* (761)
- T. ayresii* (186, 691, 762) = *Conidiosporomyces ayresii*
- T. barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & P. Syd. – *Pennisetum alopecuroides* (518); *P. orientale* (836)
- T. brachypodii-mexicani* Vánky – *Brachypodium mexicanum* (928) **isotype**
- T. brachypodii-ramosi* Zogg – *Brachypodium ramosum* (187)
- T. brefeldii* Vánky – *Muhlenbergia filiculmis* (1219) **isotype**
- T. bromi* (Brockm.) Brockm. – *Bromus mollis* (105 **isoneo-type**)
- T. bromi* (763) = *T. lolii*
- T. caries* (DC.) Tul. & C. Tul. – *Triticum aestivum* (1033)
- T. cerebrina* Ellis & Everh. – *Deschampsia cespitosa* (134, 235, 977)
- T. chionachnes* Vánky, C. Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Chionachne cyathopoda* (1083) **isotype**
- T. controversa* J.G. Kühn – *Elymus hispidus* (21, 412); *Hordeum glaucum* (764); *Triticum aestivum* (528)
- T. decipiens* (39) = *T. sphaerococca*
- T. ehrhartae* P.H.B. Talbot – *Ehrharta calycina* (474)
- T. eragrostiellae* Vánky, C. Vánky & N.D. Sharma – *Eragrostiella bifaria* (929) **isotype**

- T. flectens* Lagerh. – *Deschampsia flexuosa* (135) **topotype**
T. fusca (105) = *T. bromi*
T. holci (Westend.) J. Schröt. – *Holcus lanatus* (non *H. mollis*, 101); *H. mollis* (765)
T. horrida Takah. – *Oryza sativa* (1082)
T. hyalospora (930) = *Ingoldiomyces hyalosporus*
T. laevis J.G. Kühn – *Triticum aestivum* (766)
T. lolii Auersw. ex G. Winter – *Lolium rigidum* (767)
T. lolii (94) = *T. triticina*
T. loliolii Vánky, Carris, Castlebury & H. Scholz (in press) – *Lolium subulatum* (763)
T. menieri Hariot & Pat. – *Phalaris arundinacea* (581)
T. microtuberculata Vánky – *Muhlenbergia pulcherrima* (1220) **isotype**
T. muhlenbergiae G.P. Clinton – *Muhlenbergia microsperma* (1221)
T. nigrifaciens Langdon & Boughton – *Phragmites australis* (1152)
T. olida (Riess) J. Schröt. – *Brachypodium pinnatum* (153, 188, 291, 358, 475, 529, 582); *B. sylvaticum* (530)
T. opaca Syd. & P. Syd. – *Spinifex littoreus* (837)
T. polypogonis Vánky & N.D. Sharma – *Polypogon monspeliensis* (931) **isotype**
T. rugispora Ellis – *Paspalum plicatulum* (1092)
T. savilei R.V. Ghande & Vánky – *Tripogon jacquemontii* (859) **isotype**
T. separata J. Kunze ex G. Winter – *Apera spica-venti* (136)
T. sesleriae Juel – *Sesleria coerulea* (860); *S. rigida* (413)
T. setariae (932) = *T. thirumalachari*
T. setariae L. Ling – *Setaria viridis* (292)
T. sphaerococca (Wallr.) A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Agrostis capillaris* (39)
T. sterilis Ule – *Festuca valesiaca* (92)
T. sumatiae (S.D. Patil & Gandhe) Vánky – *Coix lacryma-jobi* (838 **topotype**, 933)
T. thirumalachari Gandhe – *Setaria intermedia* (932);
T. trachypogonis Durán – *Trachypogon spicatus* (1134)
T. triticina Ranoj. – *Haynaldia villosa* (94)
T. viennotii Syd. – *Briza maxima* (1034)
T. whiteochloae R.G. Shivas & Vánky – *Whiteochloa cymbiformis* (1087) **isotype**
- Tolyposporella**
T. chrysopogonis G.F. Atk. – *Sorghastrum stipoides* (1173)
T. pachycarpa (Syd.) L. Ling – *Coelorachis rottboelloides* (1035)
- Tolyposporium**
T. aterrimum (293) = *Moreaua aterrima*
T. bullatum (35) = *Moesziomyces bullatus*
T. caustidis (978) = *Moreaua caustidis*
T. cyatochaetae (979) = *Moreaua cyatochaetae*
T. evandrae (980) = *Moreaua evandrae*
T. gabniae (981) = *Moreaua gabniae*
T. gymnoschoeni (982, 1036) = *Moreaua gymnoschoeni*
T. junci (J. Schröt.) Woronin ex J. Schröt. – *Juncus bufonius* (107, 583)
- T. kochianum* (189, 861) = *Moreaua kochiana*
T. lepidospermae (983, 1037) = *Moreaua lepidospermae*
T. littorale (768) = *Moreaua littoralis*
T. mauritianum (984) = *Moreaua mauritiana*
T. megaglomerulosum (985, 1038) = *Moreaua megaglomerulosa*
T. muellerianum (986) = *Moreaua muelleriana*
T. neillii (G. Cunn.) Vánky & McKenzie – *Isolepis nodosa* (1016)
T. penicillariae (154) = *Moesziomyces bullatus*
T. restifaciens (414) = *Fulvisporium restifaciens*
T. rhynchosporae-cephalotis (862) = *Moreaua rhynchosporae-cephalotis*
T. rodwayi (987, 988, 989) = *Moreaua rodwayi*
T. schoeni (990) = *Moreaua schoeni*
T. tetrariae (991) = *Moreaua tetrariae*
- Tracya**
T. hydrocharidis Lagerh. – *Hydrocharis morsus-ranae* (32, 359 & 359/b, 360)
- Tranzscheliella**
T. comburens (F. Ludw.) Vánky & McKenzie – *Danthonia eriantha* (1147); *D. setacea* (994)
T. hypodytes (Schltld.) Vánky & McKenzie – *Bromus erectus* (543, 637); *Elymus hispidus* (7, 705, 877); *E. repens* (198, 434, 544, 638, 706, 785); *Leymus arenarius* (433, 707); *Lygeum spartum* (314, 491, 878); *Poa cita* (1049); *Stipa mucronata* (937); *S. papposa* (1110); *S. pennata* (639)
T. minima (Arthur) Vánky – *Achnatherum splendens* (493, 640); *Stipa dasyphylla* (1182); *S. occidentalis* (710); *S. pulcherrima* (436)
T. sparti (Massenot) Vánky – *Lygeum spartum* (492)
T. williamsii (Griffiths) Dingley & Versluys – *Stipa joannis* (450); *S. sabulosa* (324); *S. teretifolia* (900)
- Trichocntractia**
T. utriculicola (Henn.) M. Piepenbr. – *Rhynchospora corymbosa* (813, 1068)
- Urocystis**
U. agropyri (Preuss) A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Elymus farctus* (769); *E. repens* (13, 155, 190, 236, 531, 584, 692)
U. alopecuri A.B. Frank – *Alopecurus pratensis* (93, 156, 476, 863)
U. alstroemeriae Vánky & C. Vánky – *Alstroemeria pallida* (1080) **isotype**
U. anemones (Pers. : Pers.) G. Winter – *Anemone blanda* (294); *A. nemorosa* (37, 137)
U. anemones (693) = *U. pseudoanemones*
U. arrhenatheri (67) = *U. avenae-elatioris*
U. avenae-elatioris (Kochman) Zundel – *Arrhenatherum elatius* (67)
U. beckmanniae I.E. Brezhnev – *Beckmannia eruciformis* (477)

- U. bolivari* Bubák & Gonz. Frag. – *Lolium rigidum* (770, 1148)
- U. bromi* (Lavrov) Zundel – *Bromus erectus* (864)
- U. bulbocodii* Vánky – *Bulbocodium vernum* (585) **topotype**
- U. carcinodes* (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Actaea spicata* (532)
- U. ceratocephali* Zambett. ex Vánky – *Ceratocephalus falcatus* (865)
- U. colchici* (Schltdl.) Rabenh. – *Colchicum autumnale* (1, 622)
- U. corsica* (Mayor & Terrier) Vánky – *Stipa capensis* (157, 361, 415, 771)
- U. cortusae* (Liro) Schwarzman – *Cortusa matthioli* (295)
- U. eranthidis* (Pass.) Ainsw. & Sampson – *Eranthis hyemalis* (191, 296)
- U. ficariae* (Liro) Moesz – *Ranunculus ficaria* (68, 297, 623, 772)
- U. filipendulae* (Tul.) J. Schröt. – *Filipendula vulgaris* (866)
- U. fischeri* Körn. ex G. Winter – *Carex flacca* (694); *C. panicea* (773); *C. rostrata* (298, 478, 478b, 695); *C. vesicaria* × *rostrata* (4)
- U. floccosa* (Wallr.) D.M. Hend. – *Helleborus cyclophyllus* (416); *H. dumetorum* (533); *H. odorus* (97, 299)
- U. fraseri* (157) = *U. corsica*
- U. galanthi* Pape – *Galanthus nivalis* (624) **isoneotype**
- U. hellebori-viridis* (97) = *U. floccosa*
- U. hispanica* (Syd.) Zundel – *Aegilops lorentii* (625)
- U. hypoxis* (1039, 1040) = *U. thaxteri*
- U. irregularis* (G. Winter) Sävil. – *Aconitum vulparia* (76); *A. septentrionale* (237)
- U. johansonii* (Lagerh.) Magnus – *Juncus bufonius* (46)
- U. junci* Lagerh. – *Juncus balticus* (1041); *J. pallidus* (417)
- U. juncophila* (417) = *U. junci*
- U. kmetiana* Magnus – *Viola arvensis* (300); *V. oculata* (774)
- U. leersiae* Vánky – *Leersia hexandra* (586 **isotype**, 1174)
- U. leimbachii* Örtel – *Adonis vernalis* (65)
- U. luzulae* (J. Schröt.) G. Winter – *Luzula luzuloides* (479)
- U. miyabeana* Togashi & Onuma – *Polygonatum odoratum* (627)
- U. occulta* (Wallr.) Rabenh. ex Fuckel – *Secale cereale* (587, 696)
- U. ornithogali* Körn. – *Ornithogalum orthophyllum* subsp. *kochii* (626)
- U. orobanches* (Mérat) A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Orobanche ramosa* (192, 301)
- U. paridis* (Unger) Thum. – *Paris quadrifolia* (158, 362)
- U. poae* (Liro) Padwick & Khan – *Poa silvicola* (302)
- U. poae-palustis* Vánky – *Poa palustris* (193) **isotype**
- U. polygonati* (627) – *U. miyabeana*
- U. primulae* (Rostr.) Vánky – *Primula veris* (138)
- U. primulicola* (138) = *U. primulae*
- U. pseudoanemones* Denchev, Kakish. & Y. Harada – *Anemone flaccida* (693, 1114 **topotype**)
- U. pulsatillae* (Bubák) Moesz – *Pulsatilla vulgaris* subsp. *grandis* (98); *P. pratensis* (303)
- U. ranunculi* (Libert) Moesz – *Ranunculus oreophilus* (304); *R. pilosus* (867); *R. repens* (111, 159, 305, 363, 534)
- U. ranunculi-auricomi* (Liro) Zundel – *Ranunculus auricomus* (58)
- U. sorosporioides* Körn. ex A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Pulsatilla occidentalis* (697); *Thalictrum minus* (306)
- U. syncocca* (L. Kirchner) B. Lindeb. – *Hepatica nobilis* (160, 535, 628, 775)
- U. thaxteri* Vánky – *Hypoxis acuminata* (1039 **isotype**); *H. galpinii* (1040 **isoparatype**)
- U. tothii* Vánky – *Juncus compressus* (194) **isotype**
- U. trientalis* (Berk. & Broome) B. Lindeb. – *Trientalis europaea* (307 anamorph, 308)
- U. trillii* H.S. Jackson – *Trillium smallii* (698)
- U. ulei* Magnus – *Festuca heterophylla* (480); *F. rubra* (139)
- Ustacystis**
- U. waldsteiniae* (Peck) Zundel – *Waldsteinia geoides* (629)
- Ustanciosporium**
- U. gigantiosporium* (Liro) M. Piepenbr. & Begerow – *Rhynchospora alba* (369, 595)
- U. kuwanoanum* (Togashi & Y. Maki) Vánky – *Bulbostylis hispidula* (1125)
- U. majus* (Desm.) M. Piepenbr. – *Rhynchospora alba* (879)
- U. malawicum* (Kukkonen & Gjaerum) M. Piepenbr. – *Scleria nyasensis* (1175)
- U. montagnei* (Tul. & C. Tul.) M. Piepenbr., Begerow & Oberw. – *Rhynchospora alba* (711); *R. angolensis* (1242); *R. barossiana* (1222); *R. chinensis* (712); *R. rugosa* (712)
- U. retinosporum* (Kukkonen & Gjaerum) M. Piepenbr. – *Scleria greigiifolia* (1176)
- U. rhynchosporae* Vánky – *Rhynchospora rugosa* (1042) **isotype**
- U. taubertianum* (Henn.) M. Piepenbr. & Begerow – *Rhynchospora tenuis* (1095)
- Ustilago**
- U. aeluropodis* (Trotter) Vánky – *Aeluropus littoralis* (481)
- U. affinis* Ellis & Everh. – *Stenotaphrum dimidiatum* (161); *S. secundatum* (364)
- U. agropyri* McAlpine – *Danthonia pilosa* (992)
- U. alcornii* (1090) = *U. curta*
- U. altilis* Syd. – *Triodia pungens* (418) **isoneotype**
- U. andropogonis* (195) = *Sporisorium vanderystii*
- U. anomala* (365, 419, 482, 699) = *Microbotryum anomalum*
- U. anomala* var. *carnea* (53, 140) = *Microbotryum anomalum*
- U. anomala* var. *cordae* (52, 162) = *Microbotryum cordae*
- U. aschersoniana* A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Cutandia memphitica* (630)
- U. austro-africana* Vánky & C. Vánky – *Enneapogon cenchroides* (1062) **isotype**
- U. avenae* (Pers. : Pers.) Rostr. – *Arrhenatherum elatius* (163, 366, 536); *Avena barbata* (1043); *A. sativa* (238); *A. sterilis* (420); *Hordeum murinum* (700)

- U. betonicae* (631) = *Microbotryum betonicae*
U. bistortarum (357, 421, 483, 537, 701, 776, 868) = *Microbotryum bistortarum*
U. bistortarum var. *pustulata* (11) = *Microbotryum pustulatum*
U. bistortarum var. *ustilaginea* (141) = *Microbotryum bistortarum*
U. bosniaca (632) = *Microbotryum bosniacum*
U. bouriquetii Maubl. & Roger – *Stenotaphrum dimidiatum* (993)
U. bromivora (Tul. & C. Tul.) A.A. Fisch. Waldh. – *Brachypodium distachyon* (367, 422, 484, 777); *Bromus arvensis* (538); *B. diandrus* (633); *B. gedrosianus* (634); *B. madritensis* (196, 239, 423); *B. mollis* (106, 164, 309); *B. rigidus* (165, 240, 778, 869); *B. sterilis* (90, 142, 424, 779); *B. tectorum* (485, 702, 780); *B. willdenowii* (425, 486); *Hordeum jubatum* (368)
U. buchloës Ellis & Tracy – *Bouteloua chondrosioides* (1223); *B. curtipendula* (1224)
U. bullata Berk. – *Agropyron scabrum* (588, 1044)
U. bullata (90, 106, 142, 164, 165, 193, 239, 240, 367, 368, 422, 423, 424, 425, 484, 485, 486, 538, 633, 634, 702, 777, 778, 779, 780, 869) = *U. bromivora*
U. bungeana (934) = *Microbotryum cordae*
U. calamagrostidis (Fueckel) G.P. Clinton – *Calamagrostis epigeios* (15, 143, 197, 426, 870)
U. chloridis Vánky, C. Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Chloris lobata* (1084) isotype
U. circumdata Vánky – *Muhlenbergia montana* (1225) isotype
U. coicis Bref. – *Coix lacryma-jobi* (310)
U. comburens (994, 1147) = *Tranzscheliella comburens*
U. commelinae (539, 635, 871) = *Bauerago commelinae*
U. constantineanui (Sävul.) Vánky – *Crypsis alopecuroides* (487); *C. schoenoides* (313)
U. corcontica (311, 312) = *U. striiformis*
U. cordae (488, 703) = *Microbotryum cordae*
U. cortaderiae Grodz. ex Hirschh. – *Cortaderia jubata* (935)
U. crameri Körn. – *Setaria italica* (995)
U. curta Syd. – *Tripogon loliiformis* (1090)
U. cynodonticola Vánky, R.G. Shivas & A. Witt – *Cynodon dactylon* (1190) isotype
U. cynodontis (Henn.) Henn. – *Cynodon dactylon* (78, 166, 241, 427, 428, 429, 589, 636, 781)
U. dactyloctenii Henn. – *Dactyloctenium australe* (1045) isotype
U. davisii Liro – *Glyceria fluitans* (5)
U. debiscens (936) = *Microbotryum debiscens*
U. delicata L. Ling – *Melinis ambigua* (1140)
U. drakensbergiana Vánky – *Digitaria tricholaenoides* (1046) isotype
U. dregeana Tul. & C. Tul. – *Pentstemonis curvifolia* (1047)
U. dregeanoides Vánky & C. Vánky – *Merxmüllera stricta* (1048) isotype
U. duriaeana (112) = *Microbotryum duriaeanaum*
U. echinata J. Schröt. – *Phalaris arundinacea* (540)
U. egenula Syd., P. Syd. & E.J. Butler – *Eragrostis nutans* (872) isotype
U. enneapogonis G.W. Fisch. – *Enneapogon desvauxii* (1226)
U. esculenta Henn. – *Zizania latifolia* (541, 590)
U. ewartii (1094) = *Macalpinomyces ewartii*
U. filiformis (Schrank) Rostr. – *Glyceria declinata* (704, 782); *G. fluitans* (542, 591); *G. maxima* (70, 167, 430, 431); *G. nemoralis* (316); *G. plicata* (8)
U. gardneri (873) = *Bauerago gardneri*
U. grandis Fries – *Phragmites australis* (41, 242, 489, 874)
U. heleochloae (313 isotype) = *U. constantineanui*
U. heufleri (783, 875, 876) = *Vankya heufleri*
U. hitchcockiana Zundel – *Cynodon nlemfuensis* var. *robustus* (243)
U. holostei (91) = *Microbotryum holostei*
U. hordei (Pers. : Pers.) Lagerh. – *Hordeum vulgare* (86, 784)
U. hydropiperis (432, 490) = *Sphacelotheca hydropiperis*
U. hypodytes (7, 198, 314, 433, 434, 491, 543, 544, 634, 638, 639, 705, 706, 707, 785, 877, 878, 937, 1049) = *Tranzscheliella hypodytes*
U. intercedens (879) = *Ustanciosporium majus*
U. intermedia (100, 315, 592, 880) = *Microbotryum intermedium*
U. ixophori Durán – *Ixophorus unisetus* (938)
U. longiseta (786) = *Microbotryum longisetum*
U. longissima (8, 70, 167, 316) = *U. filiformis*
U. luzulae (60, 144, 145) = *Stegocinctractia luzulae*
U. lygei (492) = *Tranzscheliella sparti*
U. lyginiae (996) = *Websdanea lyginiae*
U. major (12, 168) = *Microbotryum majus*
U. marginalis (317, 435, 708) = *Microbotryum marginale*
U. mauritiana Vánky – *Phragmites mauritianus* (1129) isotype
U. maydis (DC.) Corda – *Zea mays* (146, 593, 709, 881)
U. mexicana Ellis & Everh. – *Muhlenbergia emersleyi* (1227)
U. microstegii (939, 940) = *Sporisorium microstegii*
U. minima (436, 493, 640, 710) = *Tranzscheliella minima*
U. moenchiae-manticae (82) = *Microbotryum moenchiae-manticae*
U. montagnei var. *minor* (711, 712) = *Ustanciosporium montagnei*
U. neglecta (43, 169) = *Macalpinomyces neglectus*
U. nepalensis (787, 941) = *Microbotryum nepalense*
U. neyraudiae Mundk. – *Neiraudia arundinacea* (942); *N. reynaudiana* (1056)
U. nuda (Jensen) Kellerm. & Swingle – *Hordeum leporinum* (997); *H. vulgare* subsp. *agriocrithon* (1098)
U. onopordi (882) = *Microbotryum onopordi*
U. ornithogali (34, 437, 438, 439, 494, 788, 883) = *Vankya ornithogali*
U. oxalidis Ellis & Tracy – *Oxalis stricta* (38, 113)
U. pamirica Golovin – *Bromus gracillimus* (789)
U. panici-geminati (884) = *U. rickeri*
U. panici-virgati Vánky – *Panicum virgatum* (1228) isotype
U. phrygica Magnus – *Aegilops tauschii* (798), *Taeniatherum caput-medusae* (790)
U. piperi (641) = *Microbotryum piperi*

- U. polygoni-alati* (943) = *Microbotryum piperi*
U. pustulata (642, 713, 714, 791) = *Microbotryum pustulatum*
U. quitensis Lagerh. – *Cortaderia selloana* (1078)
U. rabenhorstiana (48) = *U. syntherismae*
U. reticulata (42, 199, 244, 440, 545, 594, 715, 716, 792) =
Microbotryum reticulatum
U. rhyncosporae (369, 595) = *Ustanciosporium gigantosporum*
U. rickeri G.P. Clinton – *Paspalidium geminatum* (884)
U. scabiosae (95, 170, 245, 596, 885) = *Microbotryum scabiosae*
U. schlechteri Henn. – *Enneapogon scoparius* (1189)
U. schroeteriana Henn. – *Paspalum conjugatum* (886); *P. intermedium* (1069); *P. paniculatum* (887); *P. virgatum* (888)
U. scitaminea Syd. – *Imperata cylindrica* (944); *Saccharum officinarum* (597, 643, 889); *S. spontaneum* (945)
U. scorzonerae (644, 793, 890) = *Microbotryum scorzonerae*
U. scrobiculata Liro – *Calamagrostis purpurea* (441, 645)
U. serpens (P. Karst.) B. Lindeb. – *Elymus repens* (31, 891)
U. shastense (717) = *Microbotryum shastense*
U. shiraiana Henn. – *Indocalamus debilis* (171)
U. sorghi (172) = *Sporisorium sorghi*
U. sparsa Underw. – *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (892)
U. spermophora (546, 547, 893, 1050, 1111) = *Macalpinomyces spermophorus*
U. spinificis F. Ludw. – *Spinifex hirsutus* (598)
U. sporoboli-indici L. Ling – *Sporobolus africanus* (1192); *S. pyramidalis* (1191)
U. striiformis (Westend.) Niessl – *Agrostis alba* (28); *A. canina* (495); *A. gigantea* (246); *A. stolonifera* (496); *Arrhenatherum elatius* (497); *Brachypodium sylvaticum* (1183); *Briza media* (99); *Bromus inermis* (125, 498, 549); *Calamagrostis villosa* (311, 312, 794); *Dactylis glomerata* (114, 247, 442); *Deschampsia cespitosa* (61, 894); *Festuca sulcata* (62); *Holcus lanatus* (20); *H. mollis* (646); *Phleum pratense* (718); *Poa bulbosa* (79); *P. chaixii* (59); *P. pratensis* (1112); *P. timolentis* (895); *P. trivialis* (795); *Sitanion hystrix* (719)
U. stygia (720, 721) = *Microbotryum stygium*
U. subnitens (896) = *Aurantiosporium subnitens*
U. succisae (599, 722) = *Microbotryum succisae*
U. syntherismae (Schwein.) Peck – *Digitaria adscendens* (370, 548); *D. ciliaris* (443); *D. ischaemum* (318); *D. sanguinalis* (48, 248); *D. stricta* (946); *D. ternata* (998); *D. thouaresiana* (1099)
U. tenuispora (723, 947) = *Microbotryum tenuisporum*
U. thlaspeos (96, 600) = *Thecaphora thlaspeos*
U. tonglinensis (173) = *Sporisorium tonglinense*
U. tragana Zundel – *Tragus berteronianus* (1100)
U. tragopogonis-pratensis (17, 174, 319, 371, 444, 647, 724) =
Microbotryum tragopogonis-pratensis
U. trebouxii Syd. & P. Syd. – Gramineae indet. (796)
U. trichophora (Link) Körn. – *Echinochloa colonum* (948); *E. crus-galli* (36, 320, 372, 499, 949); *E. frumentacea* (897)
U. triodiae Vánky – *Triodia microstachya* (999 isotype, 1122)
U. triraphidis Vánky – *Triraphis schinzii* (1136)
U. tritici (Pers. : Pers.) Rostr. – *Aegilops lorentii* (648); *A. triuncialis* (898); *Hordeum distichon* (550); *H. vulgare* (725, 797); *Triticum monococcum* (84)
U. tuberculata (798) = *U. phrygica*
U. tuberculiformis (799) = *Microbotryum tuberculiforme*
U. turcomanica Tranzschel ex Vánky – *Eremopyrum distans* (800)
U. vaillantii (57, 88, 445, 649, 899) = *Vankya vaillantii*
U. vetiveriae Padwick – *Vetiveria zizanioides* (950)
U. vinosa (29, 321, 446) = *Microbotryum vinosum*
U. violacea (77, 446) = *Microbotryum dianthorum*
U. violacea (116, 148, 249, 375, 448, 449) = *Microbotryum lychmidis-dioicae*
U. violacea (118, 120, 147, 373, 374, 447) = *Microbotryum violaceum*
U. violacea (10, 117, 119, 149, 250) = *Microbotryum silenes-inflatae*
U. violacea (322, 323) = *Microbotryum stellariae*
U. violacea var. *stellariae* (54, 150) = *Microbotryum stellariae*
U. warmingii (200) = *Microbotryum warmingii*
U. williamsii (324, 450, 900) = *Franzscheliella williamsii*
U. xerochloae Vánky & R.G. Shivas – *Xerochloa imberbis* (1000) isotype
Ustilentyloma
U. fluitans (Liro) Vánky – *Glyceria fluitans* (500); *G. plicata* (80, 325, 650)
Vankya
V. heufferi (Fuckel) Ershad – *Erythronium albidum* (875); *Tulipa montana* (876); *T. polychroma* (783)
V. ornithogali (J.C. Schmidt & G. Kunze) Ershad – *Gagea arvensis* (437); *G. confusa* (883); *G. dubia* (788); *G. lutea* (438); *G. pratensis* (34, 439); *G. pusilla* (494)
V. vaillantii (Tul. & C. Tul.) Ershad – *Muscari botryoides* (899); *M. comosum* (88); *M. neglectum* (1250); *Scilla bifolia* (57, 649); *S. siberica* (445)
Websdanea
W. lyginiae (Websdane, Sivasith., K.W. Dixon & Pate) Vánky – *Lyginia barbata* (996)